

ASSESSMENT AND TESTING IN EFL CLASSROOM OF PRE- INTERMEDIATE LEVEL STUDENTS

Alisherova Shahnoza Asqarovna

a second year student of master's degree of
the department foreign language and literature of
the faculty of Foreign philology of National university of Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10208305>

Assessment and testing are important components of EFL classrooms as they allow teachers to evaluate their students' language proficiency and progress. Pre-intermediate level students are typically at a stage where they have a basic understanding of English grammar and vocabulary, but may still struggle with more complex language structures and expressions.

Some common types of assessments and tests used in EFL classrooms for pre-intermediate level students include:

1. Placement tests: These are used to determine the students' level of English proficiency and ensure they are placed in the appropriate class.
2. Diagnostic tests: These are used to identify specific areas of weakness or strengths in the students' language skills, such as grammar, vocabulary, reading comprehension, or listening comprehension.
3. Formative assessments: These are ongoing assessments used to monitor the students' progress throughout the course. They can include quizzes, homework assignments, class participation, and oral presentations.
4. Summative assessments: These are used to evaluate the students' overall performance at the end of the course or a specific unit. They can include final exams, essays, or projects.

When designing assessments and tests for pre-intermediate level students, it is important to consider their language proficiency level and ensure that the tasks are appropriate for their abilities. Tasks should also be varied to accommodate different learning styles and provide opportunities for students to demonstrate their skills in different ways.

Overall, assessment and testing are important components of EFL classrooms for pre-intermediate level students. Teachers should use a variety of assessment methods to evaluate their students' language proficiency and progress, while also ensuring that tasks are appropriate for their abilities.

Here are some additional tips and considerations for assessment and testing in EFL classrooms for pre-intermediate level students:

1. Use authentic materials: Incorporate authentic materials, such as news articles, videos, or podcasts, into assessments and tests to provide students with real-world language practice.

2. Provide feedback: Provide timely and constructive feedback to students on their assessments and tests to help them improve their language skills.

3. Consider cultural differences: Be mindful of cultural differences when designing assessments and tests. Avoid using culturally-specific references or topics that may be unfamiliar to students.

4. Use technology: Utilize technology, such as online quizzes or interactive activities, to engage students and provide them with immediate feedback.

5. Encourage self-assessment: Encourage students to self-assess their language skills and progress throughout the course. This can help them take ownership of their learning and identify areas where they need improvement.

6. Collaborate with colleagues: Collaborate with other teachers or language experts to design assessments and tests that align with the course objectives and standards.

By considering these tips and incorporating a variety of assessment methods, teachers can effectively evaluate their pre-intermediate level students' language proficiency and progress, while also providing them with opportunities to improve their skills in a supportive learning environment.

Assessing learners' outcomes is not an easy task since. Every single teacher has a different view of what assessing is, and each teacher may have a different thought of what this process implies. However, there is something which seems to be a common element: evaluation is a natural activity. "Evaluation is not restricted to the context of education; it is part of our everyday

lives" (Dickins & Germaine. 1992, p: 3). Taking this into account, we might say that we are on an implicit process of evaluating and assessing our daily life trying to understand people, actions, phenomena, etc., and of course our teaching and learning development. The assumptions we gather from lifetime experience are linked to our understanding of the nature of language teaching and learning. This article aims to devise a formal progress or achievement test for assessing language learning outcomes. It is divided into two parts. The first one is a rationale that intends to discuss different aspects of what evaluation, assessment and testing involve when designing an achievement or progress test in order to draw conclusion to expand our teaching practices and subsequently our evaluation activities. The second part

is a progress test designed for the purpose of assessing language learning outcomes.

This test does not require much equipment or people to be administered; therefore it is easy to put into practice. Although this is not a formal test, the consistency of a test depends on the formal arrangement of it, an effect on the student's performance is expected regarding their learning process since it is part of an academic term of the course. The test is intended to expand a bit more the information gathered during the course about the learning processes of the learners. The test does not seek to get a final score, but more information about the students' performance in order to describe observation in each of the language skills evaluated. Integrative objectives techniques are implied in the test such multiple choice questions in the reading and usage section. Performance and authenticity of the texts used in the test show that subjective testing techniques are implemented. On the other hand, developing a language test depends on the purpose for which that test is intended. We need to work out what we are going to assess, and then establish clear criteria for doing so, and lastly link this process with a formal assessment to give more reliability for getting effectiveness to the formal educational program as Bachman stated (1990) However, it is sometimes quite difficult to select the right way to assess our students because each of them bring a specific condition of learning and each teacher his/her own way of assessing his/her students. Here informal assessment encounters a barrier which is developing a set of criteria to help describe students' performance. On the other hand, there is something that must be discussed. To what extent an informal devise may assess our learners' outcomes? To what extent is that test valid? Is it feasible to final assess the learning of a language? And here the old discussion that Bachman mentioned about what is learnable is measurable. At this point, we also have to consider the type of testing we need to attain so, and whether the information provided by the tests are of good quality to make correct decisions to monitor our learners' learning process or to improve the educational program.

To draw my own conclusions on this subject, one might say that there is no right way to assess our students' performance in language learning. However, I think that even though that every teacher has his/her particular way to judge the way learners progress and perform their knowledge, assessment is necessary to monitor their outcomes at least in a qualitative way to build a summative evaluation not only on the learners but on the decision making for the educational program. Finally, with the completion of this assignment I could

realize that evaluation puts together different elements that influence the teaching and learning of a language starting from content of the course, objectives, course design, materials, methodology as well as teacher performance.

References:

- 1.Rea-Dickins & Kevin Germaine. Evaluation. Oxford University Press. 1992.
- 2.Bachman Lyle F. Fundamental Considerations in Language Testing. Oxford University Press.1990.
- 3.<http://www.cnn.com/2007/WORLD/americas/09/19/chavez.colombia.ap/index.html> (Wed September 19, 2007)
4. Mufftah, A. (1994). Developing student' s listening comprehension. paper presented at the TESOL Convention, Maryland, Baltimore, USA, March.
- 5.Mullis, I. (1992). Developing the NAEP content area frameworks and innovative assessment. Journal of Educational measurement; Vol. 29 (2) p 11-131.
- 6.The National Assessment of Educational Progress. (1992). Educational Testing Service. U.S.A. Developing the NAEP content area framework and innovative assessment methods in the 1992 assessments in mathematics, reading and writing. Princeton. N.J, US.
7. National Council of Teachers of English (NCTE) English for Today, (1972). Book 1: At Home and At School 2nd ed. (New York; McCraw Hill Book Company, 1972.
- 8.Navarrette, C.; J. Wilde, C. Nelson C.;R. Martinez Hargett C. (1990). Informal Assessment in Education: Implications For Bilingual Education Programs. National Clearing for Bilingual Education.Summer.
- 9.Newman, C. ; L. Smolen. (1993). Portfolio Assessment in our Schools: Implementation. Advantages. and Concerns. Midwesrtern Educational Researcher; v6 nl p28-32 Win.
10. Nolet, V. (1992). Classroom-Based Measurement and Portfolio Assessment. Diagnostique; Vol.18, nl, p5-26, Fall.